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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Architect / Built heritage specialist Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor Condition

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Conditions

Architect / Built heritage specialist Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Architect / Built heritage specialist Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital

Main Difficulties in Sharing data

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Architect / Built heritage specialist
3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Use of 3D Models

Use of Digital Simulation

Main Challenges in Integrating Digital Technologies

Architect / Built heritage specialist
Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

Areas where Digital Twins are considered Most Useful

Information or Support expected from Reactive Digital Twins

Future Evolution of Digital Twin

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Architect / Built heritage specialist

Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	Geometric data (architectural surveys, point clouds, 2D/3D drawings)	Structural data (load assessments, deformation monitoring, material properties)	Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollution, wind, etc.)	Historical documentation (construction phases, archives, restoration history)	Material analysis results (e.g., stratigraphy, decay mapping, tests on mortars or stones)	Photographic documentation (orthophotos, visual inspections, condition mapping)	GIS and geospatial data (site context, topography, zoning)
Photogrammetry tools	20	7	6	19	14	19	9
3D scanning tools (e.g., LIDAR, structured light)	20	8	5	17	13	17	9
Building Information Modeling (BIM) software (e.g., Revit, ArchiCAD)	12	6	3	12	9	11	6
CAD software for architectural documentation (e.g., AutoCAD)	26	9	5	27	18	24	12
GIS tools for mapping and spatial analysis	13	3	3	14	11	14	11
Software for structural analysis or simulation	6	4	1	5	5	3	2
Thermographic or multispectral imaging for diagnostics	10	4	5	10	8	9	3
Digital tools for heritage condition surveys	8	3	4	8	6	8	5
I do not use digital tools	2	1	2	4	3	3	2

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Yes, continuously (e.g., from sensors or automated systems)	Yes, but only in specific situations or scheduled intervals	No, data are collected manually or post-processed after sampling	I'm not sure / Not applicable	MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Difficulty obtaining accurate and reliable data	Lack of adequate or appropriate tools/technologies	High cost of equipment and maintenance	Complexity in interpreting collected data	Integration difficulties between traditional and digital practices	Technical maintenance of monitoring systems	I do not face major difficulties
Photogrammetry tools	1	7	8	4	3D laser scanning or structural surveying tools	6	4	15	8	11	5	0
3D scanning tools (e.g., LIDAR, structured light)	1	8	7	4	Crack monitors or displacement sensors	5	2	4	3	3	3	0
Building Information Modeling (BIM) software (e.g., Revit, ArchiCAD)	0	8	4	2	Environmental sensors (e.g., temperature, humidity, pollutants)	4	6	4	6	5	6	0
CAD software for architectural documentation (e.g., AutoCAD)	1	10	14	4	Remote sensing platforms	2	3	2	1	1	4	0
GIS tools for mapping and spatial analysis	1	6	7	1	I do not use digital tools for monitoring	1	3	3	2	3	1	2
Software for structural analysis or simulation	0	4	1	1								
Thermographic or multispectral imaging for diagnostics	1	7	2	0								
Digital tools for heritage condition surveys	1	3	3	1								
I do not use digital tools	0	1	0	3								

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Unstructured files (PDF, Word, etc.)	Structured datasets (CSV, Excel)	Relational databases	GIS and geospatial data	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	BIM formats (e.g., IFC, RVT)	Proprietary formats from specific software (e.g., CAD, Revit)	COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing	Lack of adequate digital infrastructure for data storage and access	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Limited collaboration among professionals or institutions	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Geometric data (architectural surveys, point clouds, 2D/3D drawings)	24	21	5	10	19	9	24	Yes, platforms internal to my institution	8	5	6	4	3	1
Structural data (load assessments, deformation monitoring, material properties)	6	7	2	3	7	4	9	Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Trello, GitHub, BIM 360, etc.)	5	1	0	1	4	0
Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollution, wind, etc.)	8	10	2	3	6	2	6	No, but I'd be interested in using them	6	5	6	1	7	1
Historical documentation (construction phases, archives, restoration history)	26	21	6	11	18	7	24	No, I don't see their usefulness	3	2	1	0	2	1
Material analysis results (e.g., stratigraphy, decay mapping, tests on mortars or stones)	18	17	3	10	14	6	16							
Photographic documentation (orthophotos, visual inspections, condition mapping)	23	20	4	11	19	7	22							
GIS and geospatial data (site context, topography, zoning)	13	12	3	10	10	4	10							

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	High costs for equipment, software, or training	Lack of technical skills within the team	Resistance to change by heritage professionals or institutions	Difficulty interpreting or managing digital data	Interoperability issues between traditional and digital workflows	No significant difficulties	3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Real-time condition monitoring of built heritage assets	Simulation of environmental or structural impact on buildings	Planning and testing restoration or conservation interventions	Integration of diagnostic data with architectural models	Risk assessment and emergency preparedness	Documentation for long-term maintenance and policy making	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	11	6	10	7	7	0	Yes, frequently	13	10	15	9	10	9	0
Yes, occasionally	13	9	8	5	9	0	Yes, occasionally	14	10	12	11	10	12	0
No, but I would be interested	2	1	1	0	1	0	No, but I would be interested	2	1	1	1	1	1	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	High costs for equipment, software, or training	Lack of technical skills within the team	Resistance to change by heritage professionals or institutions	Difficulty interpreting or managing digital data	Interoperability issues between traditional and digital workflows	No significant difficulties	SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Current condition data (e.g., structural monitoring, 3D scans)	Predictive modeling of deterioration based on environmental input	Virtual testing of design or conservation actions	Integration with historical plans, documentation, and regulations	Alerts and notifications for critical structural or environmental changes	Tools for collaboration between institutions on interoperable models
Yes, frequently	6	4	5	5	3	0	Yes, frequently	7	7	6	8	7	6
Yes, occasionally	8	6	7	5	10	0	Yes, occasionally	11	9	9	8	5	5
No, but I would be interested	12	6	7	2	4	0	No, but I would be interested	9	8	6	7	9	8
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0